

Complexes of Tin(IV) Halides with Substituted Arylazo-2-pyridine

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Recently, we have synthesised a series of diorganotin(IV) complexes of the types $R_2SnCl_2 \cdot L$ and $(R_2SnL_2)(ClO_4)_2$ ^{1,2}; and triorganotin(IV) complexes of the types $R_3SnCl \cdot L$ and $(R_3SnL)(ClO_4)_3$ where $R=Me$ or Ph and L represents substituted arylazo-2-pyridine. In continuation of earlier work, we report herein the synthesis of complexes of composition $SnX_4 \cdot L$ where $X=Cl, Br$ or I and L arylazo-2-pyridines, viz. L^1 phenylazo-, L^2 *m*-tolylazo-, L^3 *p*-tolylazo-, L^4 *p*-chlorophenylazo-2-pyridines.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are coloured solids, insoluble in most of the organic solvent but soluble in DMF and DMSO. The molar conductance values (Table 1) of the complexes reveal their non-electrolytic nature. Analytical and spectroscopic data suggests that the complexes are anhydrous and free from coordinated or lattice water.

Arylazo-2-pyridine exists as stable *trans* isomeric form and possesses azo and pyridine nitrogen atoms, both able to coordinate to tin atom^{1,2}. In view of this, structural informations have been extracted from ir, ¹H nmr and ¹¹⁹Sn Mössbauer spectroscopic data.

The $\nu_{C=N}$ band of the ligands (1 604–1 570 cm^{-1}) found splitted in the complexes, indicates coordination of pyridine nitrogen atom to $Sn^{1,2}$. A shift of ligand $\nu_{N=N}$ band to lower wavenumber in the complexes at 1 400 cm^{-1} , confirms the participation of one of the azo-nitrogens in the coordination^{1,2}. The bands due to ν_{Sn-X} have been assigned as shown in Table 1, while ν_{Sn-N} could not be assigned with reasonable certainty.

¹H nmr spectra of the complexes show the presence of ligand aromatic and aliphatic protons. The ligand proton adjacent to pyridine nitrogen atom shifted significantly to downfield (Table 1) indicating the coordination of the pyridine nitrogen atom¹. The other signals due to ligand aromatic protons were not generally distinguishable and record as multiplets.

¹¹⁹Sn Mössbauer spectra of some representative complexes have been recorded to provide further structural evidence in support of the proposed structure. The SnX_4 complexes of L show isomer shifts of ~ 0.43 ($X=Cl$), ~ 0.56 ($X=Br$) and ~ 0.62 ($X=I$) $mm\ s^{-1}$ which are less positive than that observed for the corresponding SnX_4 compounds³, indicating a decrease in the *s*-electron density on going from the four- to six-coordinated species.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	M.p. (°C)/ (colour)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Cond. ^a $\Omega^{-1}\ cm^{-1}$ mol^{-1}	ν_{max}			δ
		C	H	N	Sn		C=N	N=N	(Sn-X)	
$L^1 \cdot SnCl_4$	>200 (Yellow)	29.70 (29.75)	2.05 2.02	9.50 9.46	26.65 26.75)	12	1 604, 1 597	1 390	326	9.10 ^b
$L^2 \cdot SnCl_4$	>200 (Deep brown)	31.65 (31.46)	2.43 2.40	9.10 9.17	25.81 25.93)	8	1 603, 1 572	1 408	326	8.80 ^b 2.60 ^c
$L^3 \cdot SnCl_4$	>200 (Yellow)	31.30 (31.46)	2.38 2.40	9.16 9.17	25.89 25.93)	10	1 603, 1 576	1 402	333	9.10 ^b 2.80 ^c
$L^4 \cdot SnCl_4$	>200 (Brick red)	27.50 (27.60)	1.59 1.67	8.80 8.78	24.71 24.82)	8	1 597	1 397	325	8.90 ^b
$L^1 \cdot SnBr_4$	149 (Brown)	21.22 (21.24)	1.38 1.44	6.71 6.76	19.01 19.10)	10	1 593	1 391	272	9.15 ^b
$L^2 \cdot SnBr_4$	>200 (Brick red)	24.61 (24.55)	1.70 1.73	6.60 6.61	18.61 18.68)	11	1 602, 1 583	1 409	272	9.27 ^b 2.60 ^c
$L^4 \cdot SnBr_4$	>200 (Orange)	20.18 (20.12)	1.20 1.19	6.38 6.40	18.02 18.10)	10	1 604, 1 586	1 403	277	9.03 ^b
$L^1 \cdot SnI_4$	175 (Brownish orange)	16.28 (16.31)	1.10 1.11	5.20 5.19	14.60 14.66)	8	1 600, 1 591	1 395	234	8.90 ^b
$L^3 \cdot SnI_4$	>200 (Brown)	18.78 (18.67)	1.38 1.31	5.00 5.02	14.18 14.21)	12	1 598	1 407	235	8.89 ^b 2.30 ^c
$L^4 \cdot SnI_4$	179 (Deep brown)	15.55 (15.64)	1.00 0.95	4.90 4.97	14.00 14.06)	8	1 598	1 403	235	8.92 ^b

^aIn DMF. ^{b,c}Refers to the ligand protons adjacent to pyridine nitrogen atom and CH_3 protons, respectively, in acetone- d_6 solvent.